

D8.12 Final Public Communication Materials

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Project title	Safe and effective human-robot cooperation towards a better competitiveness on current automation lack manufacturing processes.
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Revision History

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	14/12/2021	Marina Presas (EUT)	Deliverable writing
1.0	14/12/2021	Simona Neri (Project Coordinator EUT)	Submission

Executive Summary

As the project coordinator of Sharework project Simona Neri informed the Project Officer the past December 1st 2021 via email, the submission date of Deliverable 8.12, to be submitted according to the project plan by the end of December 2021, is not correct.

This deliverable was planned to be submitted by the end of the project on M48, in line with D8.13 – Final PUDR and compile all new communication materials produced from M36 to M48.

Recent communication materials and activities carried out were reported on October 2021 in D8.8 – Public Communication Materials. In addition, updates on this activity were included in the technical review report and review meeting presentation during November 2021.

To our understanding, replicating the previous deliverable without new content is counter-productive, whilst this deliverable can provide valuable input to the European Commission if produced by the end of the project.

Therefore, we believe it is better to postpone the production of this deliverable by M48, when we compromise to submit it in a timely manner and with updates on communication activities.